

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

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List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
GAPPA	Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030
GPAQ	Global Physical Activity Questionnaire
MET	Metabolic equivalent of task
NCD	Non-communicable disease
PA	Physical Activity
WHO	World Health Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The fourth work package of the CITY-MOVE project aims to analyze routine data collected by partner cities to evaluate policy interventions designed to improve physical activity (PA) levels, especially among those at higher risk of inactivity. Routine data, defined as data collected regularly without a specific research purpose, provides real-world and timely information needed for evidence-based decision-making. Deliverable 4.1 proposes a template to organize data sources and select relevant data assets for CITY-MOVE.

The template is based on the World Health Organization's (WHO) Global Action Plan on Physical Activity (GAPPA), which outlines four strategic objectives: Active People, Active Systems, Active Environments, and Active Societies. From the twenty action points in which these objectives are specified, we have selected those domains relevant in terms of routine-data. The GAPPA categorizes these as indicators of policy implementation, indicators of outcome, and indicators of impact. For each routine-data domain, we have formulated a list of proposed variables to operationalize them as tangible indicators. This list of proposed variables is then used as a selection manual for mapping the routine-data of a partner city. We demonstrate this with a populated indicator table for the city of Antwerp.

When describing routine-data, three characteristics are important: the data collection level, geospatial granularity, and longitudinal availability. Data sources can be primary (collected by the city itself), or secondary, through higher-level governmental bodies (e.g., national statistics bureaus), or lower-level governmental bodies (district governmental entity) or NGOs e.g.. Geospatial granularity indicates the level of detail, ranging from one city-wide metric to detailed street-level data, while the longitudinal availability tells us whether we can compare these metrics over time.

The routine-data template will be used for all six CITY-MOVE partner cities, providing an overview of data sources, geospatial granularity, and collection frequency. The goal of this exercise is to highlight domains with robust data and identify data gaps.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. ABOUT CITY-MOVE

City environments can play a role in the non-communicable diseases (NCDs) prevalence through several intersecting social, cultural and environmental factors. Cities can influence key behaviours such as the healthiness of diet and levels of physical activity (PA). For example, transport systems, building and street designs, and land use patterns can impact NCDs through their influence on air quality, PA, blood pressure, and obesity. Cities are thus both a threat to health and a potential enabler of change. Given the untapped potential of cities to promote PA, CITY-MOVE focuses on adapting the Global Action Plan on Physical Activity (GAPPA) to the city-level (city-GAPPA).

CITY-MOVE aims to accelerate and support action for PA at the city level in six cities across three continents: Europe (Antwerp, Ljubljana, and Rotterdam), Africa (Kampala) and Latin America (Bogotá and Lima), to learn from cities in different phases and in diverse cultural and macro-economic contexts. The project investigates specifically the effects of policy interventions to improve the physical activity levels, particularly for groups at higher risk of being physically inactive.

1.2. ROUTINE-DATA MAPPING TEMPLATE

The goal of the fourth work package of CITY-MOVE is to provide a comprehensive overview of the routine data collected in each city. By routine data, we mean data that is collected without an a priori research purpose or question (Nicholls et al., 2017), specifically data collected regularly on cities' geographical territories and populations. As seen in public health research, routine data can provide timely, real-world information needed for evidence-based decision-making (Morrato et al., 2007). It is important to note that cities (and other governmental levels) collect data on a wide range of subjects and themes - often not (directly) relevant to PA. Existing research has shown that factors determining PA behaviour are diverse and vary across low-, middle- and high-income countries (Bauman et al., 2012). As CITY-MOVE is interested in the effects of policy interventions to improve PA, the purpose of Deliverable 4.1 is to provide a template to narrow down the types of data subjects and allow for a selection of data assets relevant for the research purposes of CITY-MOVE. As CITY-MOVE wants to study the effectiveness of policy interventions in regard to the goals set in the Global Action Plan on Physical Activity, the selection of relevant data from the abundance of available routine data will be based on GAPPA.

GAPPA delineates four strategic objectives—Active People, Active Systems, Active Environments, and Active Societies. These objectives are further divided into twenty actions and outcomes aimed at improving PA levels. Some outcomes and action points across these four objectives are very related. For example, the development of policy programs to improve PA (action 4.1) and the training of professionals who implement these policies (action 3.1). From these twenty action points, we can therefore distil sixteen domains, categorized according to the Global Status Report on Physical Activity as indicators of policy implementation, indicators of outcome and indicators of impact (World Health Organization, 2021). We have selected those indicators relevant for the purpose of this deliverable, i.e. selecting the indicators that are relevant from a routine-data perspective.

1.3. OPERATIONALISING THE GAPPA FRAMEWORK

Translating the GAPPA action points was done using the research underlying the GAPPA, as well as studies conducted following its publication. This involves research directly related to PA, studies specifically built around built environment indicators from an urban perspective, as well as topic-specific publications as for example air quality assessment methods. The result of this exercise is the formulation of a set of proposed indicators per domain of the GAPPA framework. However, it is to be noted that this list of indicators represents an ideal setting: it may not be possible nor necessary to have a city-specific indicator in each domain.

1.3.1. Physical activity

Measuring physical activity is the core metric to improve when assessing the behaviour change that GAPPA aims to accomplish. Looking at the strategic objectives, “Creating Active People” is defined as “Individuals and/or groups who integrate physical activity into daily routines” (World Health Organization, 2018). The goal of active living is to meet at least the global recommendation of physical activity through practices such as walking, cycling, playing, gardening and other activities that can be considered as physical activity” (World Health Organization, 2021). This domain translates into perhaps the most intuitive set of indicators, however, not always the easiest in terms of data availability.

1.3.1.1. Defining physical activity

First and foremost we start by defining physical activity and its different forms. Physical activity is in its elemental form defined as “... any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that results in energy expenditure” (Caspersen et al., 1985). Imagine a person at rest: this person consumes a certain amount of energy and has a specific level of oxygen intake. Clinically, this energy consumption is defined as the resting metabolic rate. Each activity undertaken by a person can then be expressed as the metabolic equivalent of this task (MET), describing for a certain activity in a practical and easy to understand way the comparison to the resting metabolic rate, and the exercise tolerance for each individual (Jetté et al., 1990). From the resting state, we can then specify physical activity as being of light, moderate or vigorous intensity based on the multiple of METs compared to the resting state. Light-intensity physical activity (LPA) refers to PA that is performed between, on an absolute scale, 1.5 and 3 METs. Moderate physical activity (MPA) is described as the equivalent of 3 to 6 METs, and vigorous physical activity (VPA) as 6 METs or more. Moderate-to-vigorous intensity physical activity (MVPA) is then by extension any PA performed at >3METs (Bull et al., 2020; Macintosh et al., 2021).

We find these same definitions of PA and its different forms in GAPPA and the WHO recommendations on physical activity for a healthy lifestyle (World Health Organization, 2010). The most recent evidence suggests that a normal adult should engage in 150 minutes of moderate physical activity per week (Jakicic et al., 2019), as included in GAPPA.

1.3.1.2. Measuring physical activity

Returning to routine-data, we discuss the measurement of physical activity after defining it. To produce comparable, valid and reliable data about the physical activity levels of the world's population, the WHO needed a standardized tool that allows for comparisons across culturally diverse settings. Responding to this challenge, the Global Physical Activity Questionnaire (GPAQ) was developed, comprising of 19 questions collecting information on three domains: work-related, transport-related and recreational physical activity (Armstrong & Bull, 2006). This resulted in comparable estimates for over 146 countries, though data quality can vary across countries and over time, partly due to the self-reporting nature (Guthold et al., 2018). Gathering objective data on PA levels has therefore proven to be challenging, however there is the expectation that new sources will become more globally available through smartphones and wearables, as some authors have shown (Althoff et al., 2017; Guthold et al., 2018; Keating et al., 2019).

For operationalising PA regarding routine-data gathering, we chose not to distinguish a separate metric regarding work-related physical activity, as there is limited added value for doing so in the specific setting of an urban context, and it does not relate to the policy interventions studied in CITY-MOVE. We do separate transport-related and recreational PA: both directly relate to the living environment shaped by policy, and both can be expected in routine-data practices by cities.

In populating the routine-data mapping table, we therefore followed some of the questions from GPAQ, resulting in indicators such as “minutes per week of moderate physical activity”, both for recreational and transport-related occasions, but also the number of days per week one is engaged in moderate-to-vigorous PA and the number of steps taken per day. As stated before, the indicators can be seen as an ideal scenario, though our expectation is that there will be varying extra indicators of PA in each city individually. Included in the overview is for example the number of park users: this can be measured in different ways, through a self-reported measure in which citizens state how often they visit the park monthly, or a more objective method where cities count the number of citizens visiting the park, either continuously or at specific intervals. Some indicators will report on the population, others might zoom in on a specific demographic such as adolescents.

As the specific translation of these measures can vary across cities, we want to repeat that we do not exclude measures that are not a perfect match with the proposed variables. We will sort the available indicators per city according to their category and suitability.

1.3.2. Non-communicable disease burden

To measure NCD burden and their development, we again refer to the WHO framework. The aggregating indicator in this case is the premature NCD mortality in a given city. This refers to “... the unconditional probability of dying between the ages of 30 and 70 years, from cardiovascular diseases, cancer, diabetes or chronic respiratory diseases” (World Health Organization, 2013). We can look for this specific indicator in each city or look at more specific measures focusing on one medical condition, such as mortality due to diabetes.

Translating this into routine-data, we have chosen mortality due to NCDs, as well as the prevalence of obesity, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and Chronic Inflammatory Lung Disease (COPD). The same reasoning applies for this domain: depending on the availability of these indicators per city we have alternatives, following the WHO documentation.

1.3.3. Environmental indicators

From the indicators on the individual level, we move towards the environmental factors: how can urban infrastructure help its citizens move more, be more physically active in their daily lives? This involves strengthening the integration of urban and transport planning prioritizing highly connected neighbourhoods that enable and promote walking, cycling and other forms of non-motorised transport, as well as public transportation. It includes improving walking and cycling infrastructure, assuring road and personal safety for road users, and strengthening access to good-quality public and green open spaces (World Health Organization, 2018). We present an overview of applicable and relevant routine-data indicators.

1.3.3.1. Supportive active transport environment

For encouraging active forms of transportation, it is crucial to have a proper network of roads. From a series of papers written for the Lancet Global Health, which specifically examine the implications of GAPP at the city-level, we included a set infrastructural indicators such as the ratio of roads to footpaths and street connectivity metrics, but also population density as a metric for urban sprawl (Giles-Corti et al., 2022). This was complemented by research on the walkability of city neighbourhoods by Thornton et al. (2022). From Walk21, an organization working closely together with cities worldwide on implementing WHO guidelines on walkability, we included street illumination, sense of security, and the number of pedestrian accidents (Walk21, 2019). Other proposed indicators cover pedestrian-friendly road infrastructure through low-speed zones and pedestrian zones. Indicators measuring other forms of transport include but are not limited to the proportion of the population that lives within 500 meters of a public transport stop and whether bike sharing programs exist and how much territory they cover.

1.3.3.2. Supportive recreational and sports environment

Next to having an environment that supports active transportation, we focus on the infrastructural and environmental indicators that encourage a more active lifestyle in the recreational domain. We include metrics on the proportion of the population with easy access to public open space or pedestrian network and the availability of facilities such as sports centres, soccer fields, beach fronts and parks (Giles-Corti et al., 2022; Thornton et al., 2022). It is important to note that the recreational infrastructure might vary according to local context. For instance, basketball courts might be included instead of soccer fields in the urban land mix.

1.3.3.3. Air quality

Deteriorating air quality puts pressure on living conditions in cities world-wide due to increased traffic and congestion (Walk21, 2019). Air pollution affects people's PA behaviour, and exercising under poor air quality can also increase pollutant intake and increase the risk of developing chronic lung diseases and cardiovascular diseases (Hahad et al., 2021; Tainio et al., 2021). Therefore, understanding air quality in a city is an important environmental factor influencing both PA behaviour and the general NCD risk burden. The most convenient method to measure ambient air quality is using local measurement station data spread across the country.

As these kind of measurement stations are not always available and often do not provide data detailed enough for a nuanced understanding of air pollution in an urban environment, the WHO developed alternative measurement methods requiring only a select number of measuring points to predict air quality across urban areas. We mention the Data Integration Model for Air Quality (DIMAQ), combining geophysical satellite-estimates of PM2.5 with ground-level monitors and land-use data (Shaddick et al., 2018). Another method that

could provide a solution in case of lacking measurement stations is the Machine-Learning Land-use Regression (ML-LUR) approach, using open-source satellite imagery and local traffic volume indicators to estimate ambient air pollution (World Health Organization, 2023).

1.3.3.4. Inclusivity

The reasons for varying levels of PA among people of different socio-economic status (SES) are complex and vary within and between countries, making the relationship between SES and PA not straightforward to explain (Stalsberg & Pedersen, 2018). Inclusivity, equity of access and inequality are discussed in each of the strategic objectives in GAPP and form a central pillar for a more active future. However, for many of these objectives, there are no national policies or metrics to track progress (Lowe et al., 2022; World Health Organization, 2018, 2021).

Although we have not found inclusivity metrics that fall under routine-data, we can calculate an inclusivity measure, specifically an equity of access measure, using standard routine-data indicators. Equity of access means that public spaces, green open spaces, public transport and other infrastructure requirements and policy goals should ideally be equally accessible for all inhabitants (Lowe et al., 2022). With data monitored in other domains, we can calculate such a metric, that combines different routine-data indicators to calculate an average for a certain city, and subsequently compares the divergence from the average for each neighbourhood and area.

This does not directly allow for inter-city comparisons due to variations in data availability and context but allows for an intra-city comparison and a coefficient that describes the (in)equality of access for the general population to this mix of infrastructure and amenities.

Conclusion

In the next section, we bring together all proposed indicators per domain in an overview table, and for completeness also include those domains that do not relate to routine-data. In the third section, we demonstrate the use of this table with a populated example for the city of Antwerp.

2. ROUTINE-DATA INDICATORS FOR THA GAPPA FRAMEWORK

2.1. OVERVIEW TABLE

Table 1: Overview of proposed routine-data indicators

Domain	Description	Outcome or GAPPA action(s)	Applicable ⁱ	Potential indicator(s.) to measure policy implementation, outcomes and impact regarding PA. Nb. It will not be necessary (or possible) to generate each indicator in each city
Total physical activity	Total amount of all forms of physical activity	Outcome	Yes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Minutes per week of moderate physical activity (MPA)ⁱⁱ 2. Minutes per week of vigorous physical activity (VPA)ⁱⁱⁱ 3. Minutes per week of total moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) 4. Number of days per week engaged in MVPA 5. Steps per day
Recreational physical activity	Physical activity undertaken for recreational purposes, such as recreational walking and cycling, participation in sports, etc.	Outcome	Yes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Minutes per week of light physical activity (LPA)^{iv} achieved through recreational activities (e.g. yoga, slow walking) 2. Minutes per week of moderate physical activity achieved through recreational activities 3. Minutes per week of vigorous physical activity achieved through recreational activities 4. Minutes per week of total moderate-to-vigorous physical activity achieved through recreational activities 5. Number of days per week engaged in recreational physical activity 6. Sport club membership numbers (at a city level) 7. Number of park users (at park and city level)

Transport-related physical activity	Physical activity associated with transportation, such as walking and cycling to various destinations.	Outcome	Yes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Minutes per week spent walking for transport 2. Days per week engaged in walking for transport 3. Minutes per week spent cycling for transport 4. Days per week engaged in cycling for transport 5. Mode share of walking and public transport (%) (Walk21, 2019) 6. Other means transport domain physical activity^v 7. Slope and elevation as indicators of difficulty in using active forms of transport
Non-communicable Diseases	Prevalence of NCDs such as obesity and diabetes within the population.	Outcome	Yes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Death rates unadjusted and adjusted for age caused by NCDs (World Health Organization, 2021) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.a. Prevalence of obesity & overweight 1.b. Prevalence of diabetes 1.c. Prevalence of cardiovascular disease and hypertension 1.d. Prevalence of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD)
Supportive active transport environment	Infrastructure and programs that facilitate active transportation, including road and pedestrian safety measures, cycling and walking paths, bike share programs/ infrastructure, designated speed zones, car-free roads, safe crossing points, mixed land use, and public transit stops with frequent service.	<p>Action 2.1</p> <p>Action 2.2</p> <p>Action 2.3</p>	Yes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ratio of roads (km) to footpaths (km) and designated cycle lanes (km) (Giles-Corti et al., 2022) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.a. Roads to cycling lanes ratio (avoiding overlap between footpath and "normal road") 1.b. Absolute supply of cycling lanes (kms) 2. Street connectivity; topography; road surface 3. Street illumination, police coverage, sense of security in public space, road injuries (Walk21, 2019) 4. Population density (Giles-Corti et al., 2022) 5. Population residing <500 meters from a public transport stop (%) 6. Presence and coverage of bike share programs 7. Non-motorized transport friendly infrastructure: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7.a. Shared transport initiatives (e.g. e-scooter, segways) 7.b. Presence of Speed zones 7.c. One way streets 7.d. Car free streets

Supportive recreational and sports environment	Availability of public open spaces, sports fields, playgrounds, and sports facilities such as gyms and swimming pools, in addition to the presence of trees and shaded areas.	Action 2.4	Yes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Percentage of (urban) land area allocated to open or green space (Giles-Corti et al., 2022) 2. Households within 400m distance along pedestrian network to public open space. (Thornton et al., 2022) / Percentage of population living within 500m of a public open space (Giles-Corti et al., 2021) 3. 8ha of public open space within 1km-radius (Thornton et al., 2022) 4. Publicly accessible facilities <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4.a. List of gyms / sports centres / skate parks / beach fronts / ... 4.b. Playgrounds for children 4.c. Sports fields 5. Tree coverage 6. Recreational walking / cycling tracks
Air quality	Levels of air pollutants that may affect the health outcomes of physical activity.	Outcome Action 1.2	Yes	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. DIMAQ (World Health Organization, 2023) 2. ML-LUR models; importance of link with socio-economic proxies (World Health Organization, 2023) 3. Local air quality indicators
Inclusivity	Accessibility and inclusiveness of physical activity and sports facilities for diverse populations (people with disabilities, elderly, children). Reduce burden of financial costs associated with using public transportation and accessing sports facilities, which may act as barriers to physical activity.	Action 2.2	Yes	Equity of access measure, through intra-city comparison of accessibility across neighbourhoods (Lowe et al., 2022)

Policy environment	Local, national and community policies that promote or hinder physical activity, including public health campaigns, and education policies.	Action 1.1 Action 2.3 Action 2.5 Action 3.6	No	
Physical activity programs	Physical activity programs and initiatives that engage local populations. These may be community-based, workplaces, faith-based. Patient counselling on physical activity and sedentary behaviour reduction in healthcare settings, involving trained providers and community resources. Provision of programs in other care and community settings.	Action 1.2 Action 1.3 Action 3.2 Action 3.3 Action 3.4 Action 3.5	No	
School environments	High-quality physical education and active recreation across all educational levels to promote lifelong health, physical literacy, and inclusive participation, regardless of capacity or ability.	Action 3.1	No	
Professional training	Education and ongoing training of professionals across diverse fields such as transport, urban planning, education, tourism, recreation, sports, and fitness.	Action 1.4	No	

Governance and financing	Policy frameworks, leadership and governance systems, at the national and subnational levels, to support implementation of actions aimed at increasing physical activity and reducing sedentary behaviours. Financing mechanisms to secure sustained implementation of national and subnational actions.	Action 4.1 Action 4.5	No	
Surveillance	Data systems and capabilities to support population surveillance of physical activity and sedentary behaviour and multisectoral monitoring and reporting on policy implementation.	Action 4.2	No	
Research and evaluation	Stimulate digital technologies and innovation to accelerate the development and implementation of effective policy solutions through strengthened research and evaluation capacity.	Action 4.3	No	
Advocacy	Raise awareness and drive global, regional, and national joint action among leaders, policymakers, media, and communities.	Action 4.3	No	

ⁱ As described to be measured in the World Health Organization Status Report on PA by all 194 members. This follows the idea to not place an extra burden of data monitoring on members by looking at existing, hence routine, data sources.

ⁱⁱ On an absolute scale, moderate-intensity refers to the physical activity that is performed between 3 and <6 times the intensity of rest (METs). On a scale relative to an individual's personal capacity, MPA is usually a 5 or 6 on a rating scale of perceived exertion scale of 0–10 (Bull et al., 2020).

ⁱⁱⁱ On an absolute scale, vigorous intensity refers to physical activity that is performed at 6.0 or more METs. On a scale relative to an individual's personal capacity, VPA is usually a 7 or 8 on a rating scale of perceived exertion scale of 0–10 (Bull et al., 2020).

^{iv} On an absolute scale, light intensity refers to physical activity that is performed between 1.5 and 3 METs. On a scale relative to an individual's personal capacity, light-intensity physical activity is usually a 2–4 on a rating scale of perceived exertion scale of 0–10. Examples include slow walking, bathing or other incidental activities that do not result in a substantial increase in heart rate or breathing rate (Bull et al., 2020).

^v Physical activity performed for the purpose of getting to and from places, and refers to walking, cycling and wheeling (i.e., the use of non-motorised means of locomotion with wheels, such as scooters, roller-blades, manual wheelchair, etc). In some contexts, operation of a boat for transport could also be considered transport-related physical activity (Bull et al., 2020).

2.2. DISCUSSION

2.2.1. Considerations for routine city-data

When mapping routine-data in practice, there are three specific characteristics to study. We discuss them here shortly to provide a more detailed understanding of routine-data.

2.2.1.1. Data source

From a city perspective, routine data can be collected from various sources. The most direct way method is “primary” data collection done by the city itself, which we can refer to as the central, middle level, where the city measures certain indicators directly. Secondly, data collection can be managed by a higher-level governmental body, such as a national statistics bureau, from which the city actively sources data for policy-making and reporting. Thirdly, as might specifically be the case for the data on interventions in CITY-MOVE, data collection might be undertaken by a lower-level governmental body, such as a district, or a non-governmental organization that collects data, with the data subsequently forwarded to the city level. This is schematically described in figure 1.

Figure 1: Schema of city-data source levels

2.2.1.2. Geospatial availability

A second characteristic of routine-data is its geospatial availability. This can be viewed as a spectrum. At one end, the least granular metric covers the entire city with a single indicator, such as stating the overall population density of a city as a whole. At the other end, data could be available on the street or even square meter level, providing detailed population density information per square meter. Various possibilities exist between these two extremes of the spectrum, depending on the local government structure and city structure. We represent this spectrum visually in figure 2.

Figure 2: Geospatial availability of routine-data

2.2.1.3. Longitudinal availability

A last characteristic important for describing routine-data is the longitudinal availability of a certain indicator within a city. For our research, we aim to find data that is available over longer periods of time and is updated and stored regularly. Different practices in data processing and storage across cities will be further examined in the semi-structured interviews conducted in subsequent tasks within work package 4.

2.2.2. Result of exercise: routine-data mapping

Given these considerations, the routine-data template can then be used to map the availability of indicators per domain and in each city. Making this exercise for all six cities, the resulting overview provides a comprehensive overview of the available data sources, with information on where the data was sourced, the frequency of collection and the longitudinal availability. In a subsequent phase we can consolidate the different populated templates into an overview of all six cities, allowing the identification of domains where data is robust and where data gaps exist.

As an example, we have included a filled example of the routine-data template for the city of Antwerp in section 3 of this document.

3. POPULATED EXAMPLE TABLE

Table 2: Populated example table for Antwerp

Domain	Potential indicator(s).	Data	Year Range	Source
Total physical activity	1. Minutes per week of moderate physical activity (MPA)	Survey data: active movement - District level - Every 3 years	2017 - 2023	City Monitor
	2. Minutes per week of vigorous physical activity (VPA)			
	3. Minutes per week of total moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA)			
	4. Number of days per week engaged in MVPA			
	5. Steps per day			
Recreational physical activity	1. Minutes per week of light physical activity (LPA) achieved through recreational activities (e.g. yoga, slow walking)	Survey data - % Went biking - Neighbourhood level - Every 3 years	2016 - 2019	Antwerp Monitor
	2. Minutes per week of MPA achieved through recreational activities			
	3. Minutes per week of VPA achieved through recreational activities			
	4. Minutes per week of total MVPA achieved through recreational activities			
	5. Number of days per week engaged in recreational PA			
	6. Sport club membership numbers (at a city level)			
	7. Number of park users (on a park and city level)			
	Survey data: % of population actively sporting at least 20' / week - District level - Every 2 years	2008 - 2023	City Monitor	

Transport-related physical activity	1. Minutes per week spent walking for transport	Survey data: modal split transportation - Neighbourhood level - Every 3 years	2012 - 2019	City Monitor
	2. Days per week engaged in walking for transport	Survey data: Walking as main means of transport for work - District level - Every 3 years	2014 - 2023	City Monitor
	3. Minutes per week spent cycling for transport	Survey data: Bike ownership / 1000 inhabitants - Zipcode level	2019	Mobility survey
	4. Days per week engaged in cycling for transport			
	5. Mode share of walking and public transport (%)	Mode share of public transport usage - City level - Yearly	2010 - 2023	Antwerp Monitor
	6. Other means transport domain physical activity			
	7. Slope and elevation as indicators of difficulty in using active forms of transport			
Non-communicable Diseases	1. Death rates unadjusted and adjusted for age caused by NCD's			
	1.a. Prevalence of obesity & overweight	Survey data: BMI classification with gender split - Zipcode level - Every 3 years	2013 - 2019	Antwerp Health Survey
	1.b. Prevalence of diabetes	Prevalence of diabetes / 1.000 inhabitants - Neighbourhood level - Yearly	2007 - 2022	Health Insurance Agency
	1.c. Prevalence of cardiovascular disease and hypertension	Mortality through cardiovascular diseases - District level - Yearly	2002 - 2016	Flemish Health Agency
	1.d. Prevalence of COPD	Mortality through lung diseases - District level - Yearly	2002 - 2016	Flemish Health Agency
Supportive active transport environment	1. Ratio of roads (km) to footpaths (km) and designated cycle lanes (km)	% of pedestrian friendly roads - Neighbourhood level - Yearly	2020 - 2023	Flemish Gov., Road register
	1.a. Roads to cycling lanes ratio (avoiding overlap between footpath and "normal road")	# (K)M'ers roads - Neighbourhood level - Yearly	2013 - 2023	City of Antwerp
	1.b. Absolute supply of cycling lanes (kms)	# (K)M'ers cycling lanes - Neighbourhood level - Yearly	2013 - 2023	City of Antwerp
	2. Street connectivity; topography; road surface?	Pedestrian connectivity, intersections / km ² - Area level - Yearly	2019 - 2023	Flemish Gov., Road register
	3. Street illumination, police coverage, sense of security in public space.	Survey data - % feeling unsafe in own neighbourhood - District level - Every 3 years	2008 - 2023	City Monitor
	4. Population density	Population density - Neighbourhood level - Yearly	2000 - 2024	City of Antwerp
5. Population residing <500 meters from a public transport stop (%)	% Citizens living at <5min. Walking of bus / tram stop - Neighbourhood level - Yearly	2012 - 2023	City of Antwerp, Mobility	

	<p>6. Presence and coverage of bike share programs</p> <p>7. Non-motorized transport friendly infrastructure:</p> <p>7.a. Shared transport initiatives (e.g. steps, segways)</p> <p>7.b. Speed zones</p> <p>7.c. One way streets</p> <p>7.d. Car free streets</p>	<p># Of shared bikes, public & private - City-level - Yearly</p> <p># Shared scooters / E-steps, public & private - City-level - Yearly</p> <p>Surface area speed zone (30km/h) - Neighbourhood level - Yearly</p>	<p>2010 - 2022</p> <p>2017 - 2022</p> <p>2017 - 2023</p>	<p>City of Antwerp, Mobility</p> <p>City of Antwerp, Mobility</p> <p>City of Antwerp, City Development</p> <p>Flemish Gov., Road register</p>
Supportive recreational and sports environment	<p>1. Percentage of (urban) land area allocated to open or green space</p> <p>2. Households within 400m distance along pedestrian network to public open space / Percentage of population living within 500m of a public open space</p> <p>3. 8ha of public open space within 1km-radius</p> <p>4. Other area characteristics:</p> <p>4.a. List of gyms / sports centres / skate parks / beach fronts / ...</p> <p>4.b. Playgrounds for children</p> <p>4.c. Sports fields</p> <p>4.d. Tree coverage</p> <p>5. Recreational walking tracks</p>	<p>% public green area / total area - Neighbourhood level - Yearly</p> <p>% Of citizens living <400m of public open green space - Neighbourhood level - Yearly</p> <p># of buildings dedicated to sports, commercial - Neighbourhood level - Yearly</p> <p># Playgrounds - Neighbourhood level - Yearly</p> <p># of sports halls & fields - Neighbourhood level - Yearly</p> <p>Tree coverage per height of tree - Neighbourhood level - Yearly</p>	<p>2006 - 2022</p> <p>2013 - 2024</p> <p>2010 - 2023</p> <p>2013 - 2024</p> <p>2013 - 2024</p> <p>2019 - 2024</p>	<p>City of Antwerp, City Development</p> <p>City of Antwerp, City Development</p> <p>City of Antwerp, Sports Dep.</p> <p>City of Antwerp, Sports Dep.</p> <p>City of Antwerp, Sports Dep.</p> <p>City in data</p>
Air quality	<p>1. DIMAQ</p> <p>2. ML-LUR models; importance of link with socio-economic proxies</p> <p>3. Local air quality indicators</p>	<p>Study done by Agency of Health & Care</p> <p>% Of population exposed to average NO₂-concentration >40µg/m³ on yearly basis - Area level - Every 4 years</p>	<p>2020</p> <p>2011 - 2022</p>	<p>Agency Health & Care</p> <p>City of Antwerp, Climate & Environment</p>

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